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The Efficacy and Impact of Property Crime Deterrence Strategies: A Quantitative Analysis

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Abstract

This study evaluates the efficacy and impact of property crime deterrence strategies in Trinidad, Bohol, a rural community where optimizing available law enforcement resources is essential for effective crime prevention. The research focuses on understanding how police visibility, neighborhood watch programs, surveillance technologies, and environmental design interventions influence property crime rates. Using a quantitative research design, data were collected from 120 respondents, including barangay officials, PNP personnel, and residents, through structured questionnaires. Descriptive statistics and Pearson correlation analysis were used to analyze the relationship between the perceived effectiveness of deterrence strategies and actual crime reduction. The findings reveal that stricter law enforcement, increased police visibility, and improved street lighting are perceived as the most effective measures. Community engagement in crime prevention emerged as the most impactful strategy, fostering more vital collaboration between residents and law enforcement. A significant positive correlation ($r = 0.8588$) was found between the perceived effectiveness of deterrence strategies and their impact on reducing property crime rates. The study concludes that a multifaceted approach, integrating law enforcement, community involvement, and technological interventions, offers the most comprehensive solution to property crime in rural areas. Recommendations include increasing police patrols, expanding neighborhood watch programs, upgrading surveillance infrastructure, and enhancing crime prevention education. These measures aim to strengthen Trinidad and Bohol's existing crime prevention framework and ensure sustainable reductions in property crime rates.

Keywords: Crime Prevention, Crime Reduction, Police Visibility, and Property Crime Deterrence

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INTRODUCTION

Property crime, including burglary, theft, and vandalism, poses significant challenges to communities, affecting residents' security, economic stability, and quality of life. In rural areas like Trinidad and Bohol, where resources for law enforcement and crime prevention are often limited, practical strategies for deterring property crime are especially important. Local crime data indicate fluctuations in property crime rates, underscoring the need to evaluate existing deterrence strategies thoroughly. While national statistics from the Philippine National Police show that property crimes are prevalent across urban and rural regions, most research has concentrated on urban contexts, leaving a gap in understanding the unique conditions and strategies needed for smaller communities. Addressing this gap can help local authorities in Trinidad and Bohol optimize their crime prevention approaches and allocate resources effectively.

The impact of property crime extends beyond financial loss, imposing psychological and social burdens on victims and the community. Households and small businesses face economic hardships due to the costs of replacing stolen goods or repairing damage. At the same time, the fear of crime can erode social bonds and weaken the sense of community. In smaller, rural areas, such effects can be more deeply felt, making it essential to identify the most effective crime deterrence strategies. Through a quantitative analysis of local crime data, this research aims to uncover patterns and relationships between crime rates and various deterrence strategies, including police visibility, neighborhood watch programs, surveillance technologies, and environmental design interventions. The findings will inform local policymakers, law enforcement, and community organizations about the most effective measures to reduce property crime, ensuring interventions are sustainable and tailored to the community's needs.

Research supports the study's approach by highlighting the effectiveness of integrated crime prevention strategies. Groff, Haberman, and Wood (2020) emphasize the importance of analyzing crime geographically, particularly in rural settings, where resources are limited, and targeted enforcement can make a significant difference. Her findings underscore the need for strategic police visibility in high-risk locations, which aligns with this study's focus on deploying law enforcement in specific areas of Trinidad and Bohol. Similarly, Weisburd et al. (2022), through their extensive research on hot spots policing, demonstrate that focusing law enforcement efforts in areas with higher crime concentrations significantly reduces crime in urban and rural settings. This evidence further reinforces the study's aim to examine targeted policing measures in Trinidad and Bohol and the efficient allocation of resources in areas with the highest crime rates.

Braga, MacDonald, and Barao (2021) also highlight the importance of combining law enforcement strategies with community-based approaches and environmental design interventions. His research shows that integrating neighborhood engagement, such as neighborhood watch programs, with environmental modifications, such as improved lighting and surveillance, significantly enhances crime prevention outcomes. This supports the study's examination of community participation and environmental interventions in Trinidad and Bohol, ensuring a comprehensive approach to crime deterrence.

Several other researchers also contribute to the understanding of these strategies. For instance, Welsh and Farrington (2009) systematically reviewed surveillance-based measures like closed-circuit television (CCTV). While these strategies reduced property crime in urban areas, they were less effective in rural settings, reinforcing the need for context-specific strategies. Cozens, Saville, and Hillier (2005) demonstrated that Crime Prevention Through Environmental Design (CPTED), including natural surveillance and improved lighting, can be a cost-effective approach, especially in rural communities like Trinidad, Bohol when combined with community and law enforcement efforts. Bennett, Holloway, and Farrington (2008) further support the role of community-based approaches. They found neighborhood watch programs effective in reducing property crime, particularly burglary. Their findings suggest that community involvement can enhance formal law enforcement efforts, which is a key aspect of this study, which assesses neighborhood watch initiatives as part of a broader crime prevention strategy.

Braga, Papachristos, and Hureau (2014) also emphasized the success of "hot spots" policing in reducing property crime through targeted efforts, though they caution against the displacement effect, where crime shifts to nearby areas. The current study will address this concern by assessing the broader impact of deterrence measures across different regions of Trinidad and Bohol.

In the Philippine context, Tondo et al. (2020) emphasized the effectiveness of community-oriented policing in crime reduction, highlighting the importance of collaboration between law enforcement and community members. Their findings suggest that similar strategies could be adapted for smaller communities like Trinidad and Bohol, where fostering strong police-community relationships can enhance crime prevention efforts. Laycock (2014) further concluded that situational crime prevention measures, such as CCTV and street lighting, are effective but require ongoing maintenance and community support to sustain their benefits over time. The insights from these researchers support the current study's aim to evaluate the effectiveness of various deterrence strategies in Trinidad and Bohol and identify areas for improvement. By grounding the research in established criminological theories—Routine Activity Theory, Rational Choice Theory, and Situational Crime

Prevention Theory—the study seeks to bridge the gap between theoretical concepts and practical crime prevention strategies. The findings will provide localized evidence to guide the development of policies that enhance public safety and improve the quality of life in the community.

Research Questions

The primary objective of this study was to assess the efficacy and impact of various property crime deterrence strategies in reducing property crime rates. Specifically, the study aimed to address the following research questions:

1. What are the demographic characteristics of the respondents, including:
 - 1.1 sex; and
 - 1.2 Age?
2. What is the level of efficacy of the implemented property crime deterrence strategies?
3. How does implementing property crime deterrence strategies impact current property crime rates?
4. Is there a significant relationship between the perceived efficacy of property crime deterrence strategies and current property crime rates?
5. What recommendations for improvement can be proposed based on the findings of the study?

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

This study utilized a quantitative research design to assess the effectiveness of property crime deterrence strategies in Trinidad and Bohol. The approach collected numerical data to identify patterns and relationships between deterrence measures (such as police visibility, neighborhood watch programs, surveillance technologies, and environmental design) and property crime rates. Routine Activity Theory, Rational Choice Theory, and Situational Crime Prevention Theory guided us—the research aimed to understand how these strategies influenced crime.

Research Environment and Research Participants

The study was conducted in Trinidad, a rural municipality in Bohol, Philippines, known for its residential, agricultural, and small commercial areas. The community experiences unique socio-economic and geographic challenges, with limited law enforcement resources compared to urban centers. Fluctuations in property crime rates in Trinidad highlighted the need to evaluate the effectiveness of existing crime deterrence strategies, making it a suitable setting for this research.

The research involved 120 participants, including barangay officials, PNP personnel, and community residents, to provide insights into various deterrence measures' impact and perceived effectiveness. Barangay officials and PNP personnel were included due to their roles in implementing and enforcing crime prevention strategies. At the same time, residents were selected because they are directly affected by property crimes and can offer valuable perspectives on how these crimes influence their daily lives and sense of security. By focusing on the experiences of all three groups, the study aimed to capture a comprehensive view of the community's perceptions and experiences with crime, ensuring that the findings reflect the effectiveness of local crime prevention strategies from multiple perspectives.

Research Instrument

The primary research instrument used in this study was a structured survey questionnaire designed to collect quantitative data from the respondents. The questionnaire consisted of three main sections:

1. *Demographic Information.* This section gathered data on the respondents' sex and age. It aimed to profile the participants and provide context for analyzing the responses.
2. *Perceptions of Deterrence Strategies.* This section included items measuring the respondents' views on the effectiveness of various property crime deterrence measures, such as police visibility, neighborhood watch programs, surveillance technologies, and environmental design. Likert scale questions ranging from "very ineffective" to "very effective" were used to quantify the perceived efficacy of these strategies.
3. *Impact of Deterrence Strategies on Reducing Property Crimes.* This section explored respondents' experiences and observations related to property crimes in the area. It included questions on the frequency and types of property crimes encountered, the perceived effectiveness of deterrence strategies in mitigating these crimes, and their overall impact on the community.

The questionnaire was pre-tested to ensure clarity, reliability, and validity before being administered to the 120 respondents. The data collected from the survey provided the basis for the quantitative analysis used to evaluate the relationship between deterrence strategies and their impact on reducing property crime rates in Trinidad and Bohol.

Data Analysis

To analyze the data collected in this study, the following statistical treatments were applied:

1. Descriptive Statistics

Frequency Distribution and Percentage. This was calculated to summarize the data on respondents' sex and age. This provided an overview of the demographic profile of PNP personnel, barangay officials, and community members.

Weighted Mean. The responses from PNP personnel, barangay officials, and community members were rated on a Likert scale to assess their perceived effectiveness. The mean scores indicated the overall efficacy level. The impact of implementing property crime deterrence strategies on crime reduction was assessed using Likert scale responses from the participants. Respondents (PNP personnel, barangay officials, and community members) rated their perceptions on the impact of the strategies in reducing crime on a survey questionnaire, and the mean scores were calculated to evaluate the overall perceived impact. The higher the mean score, the more significant the perceived reduction in property crime rates. This approach allowed the researcher to quantify respondents' subjective perceptions about how effectively these strategies have reduced property crimes, providing insight into the perceived success of the interventions.

2. Correlation Analysis

Pearson's Correlation Coefficient. This was used to test whether a significant relationship exists between the perceived efficacy of property crime deterrence strategies and the current property crime rates. This will determine whether higher perceived effectiveness is associated with lower crime rates, providing insight into the strategies' impact on crime reduction.

Data Gathering Procedure

The data-gathering procedure involved distributing structured questionnaires to 120 respondents, which included barangay officials, residents, and law enforcement officers in Trinidad, Bohol. The questionnaire was pre-tested to ensure clarity and reliability. It was divided into three sections: (1) demographic information (age and sex), (2) perceptions of the effectiveness of various property crime deterrence strategies (e.g., police visibility, neighborhood watch programs, CCTV, etc.), and (3) the impact of these strategies on property crime rates.

Respondents were selected through purposive sampling to ensure the inclusion of individuals with direct involvement or exposure to crime prevention strategies. All distributed questionnaires were retrieved, achieving a 100% response rate. The data were then encoded and analyzed using descriptive

statistics to summarize respondents' demographic profiles and perceptions of deterrence strategies' effectiveness. Additionally, Pearson's correlation coefficient was employed to examine the relationship between the perceived effectiveness of these strategies and actual property crime rates. This process ensured that comprehensive and reliable data were collected, providing a solid foundation for assessing the efficacy of property crime deterrence strategies in Trinidad and Bohol.

Ethical Considerations

Informed consent was obtained from all participants after clearly explaining the study's purpose and their rights, including the ability to withdraw at any time. Confidentiality and anonymity were strictly upheld, ensuring no personal information was disclosed. Participation was voluntary, with no pressure applied, and data were securely stored to prevent unauthorized access. The study posed no harm to participants and aimed to benefit the community by offering valuable insights into property crime deterrence strategies.

RESULTS

The study's results are presented below, including tables and interpretations for each research question. The tables show the statistical analysis conducted based on the data gathered from the residents of Trinidad, Bohol.

Table 1. Demographic Characteristics of the Respondents

Demographic Characteristics	Frequency (N=120)	Percentage
Sex		
Male	65	54.17
Female	55	45.83
Age Group		
18-30	40	33.33
31-45	50	41.67
46-60	20	16.67
61 and above	10	8.33

The demographic data shows that 54.17% of respondents are male and 45.83% are female, indicating a nearly balanced representation of genders. Most respondents fall within the 31-45 age group (41.67%), followed by the 18-30 age group (33.33%). This means that most of the study's participants are of working age, likely reflecting those most impacted by property crimes in the community. Smaller proportions of respondents are in the 46-60 age group (16.67%) and the 61 and above category (8.33%). These demographics ensure a well-rounded perspective on property crime deterrence strategies in Trinidad and Bohol.

Table 2. Perceptions Regarding the Effectiveness of Deterrence Strategies

Statements	Mean	Interpretation
1. Increased Police Visibility	4.20	Effective
2. Neighborhood Watch Programs	3.95	Effective
3. Use of Surveillance Cameras (CCTV)	3.50	Effective
4. Improved Street Lighting	4.10	Effective
5. Community Patrols by Residents	3.70	Effective
6. Stricter Law Enforcement (e.g., checkpoints)	4.30	Highly Effective
7. Installation of Alarm Systems in Homes/Businesses	3.60	Effective
8. Crime Prevention Education Programs	3.40	Moderately Effective
9. Controlling Access to Residential Areas	3.85	Effective
10. Implementation of Local Crime Prevention Ordinances	4.00	Effective
Over-all Effectivity	3.86	Effective

Table 2 presents respondents' perceptions regarding the effectiveness of various deterrence strategies in crime prevention. Overall, the strategies are perceived as effective, with a mean score of 3.86, indicating that respondents believe the strategies are generally successful in mitigating crime. Increased Police Visibility was rated with a mean score of 4.20, reflecting its perceived effectiveness in enhancing public safety. Similarly, Neighborhood Watch Programs (3.95), Use of Surveillance Cameras (CCTV) (3.50), and Improved Street Lighting (4.10) were also viewed as practical strategies, indicating that both community involvement and environmental measures are essential in crime deterrence.

Community Patrols by Residents scored 3.70, showing that local efforts to patrol neighborhoods are beneficial. The highest-rated strategy, Stricter Law Enforcement (e.g., checkpoints), received a mean score of 4.30, indicating it is perceived as highly effective, highlighting the critical role of law enforcement in crime prevention. Other measures, such as the installation of alarm systems (3.60), controlling access to residential areas (3.85), and local crime prevention ordinances (4.00), were also rated as effective, suggesting a favorable view toward both technological and legal approaches.

However, Crime Prevention Education Programs received a slightly lower mean score of 3.40, interpreted as moderately effective. This suggests that while education is valued, it may not be as impactful as other, more direct measures. Overall, the results indicate that law enforcement, community participation, and preventive measures are essential to effective crime deterrence, with stricter law enforcement being perceived as the most effective strategy.

Table 3. Impact of Property Crime Deterrence Strategies on Property Crime Rates

Statements	Mean	Interpretation
1. Effectiveness of Crime Deterrence Strategies	4.45	Very High Impact
2. Surveillance's Role in Crime Reduction	3.7	High Impact
3. Smart Home Technology and Crime Prevention	3.55	High Impact
4. Community Engagement in Crime Prevention	4.75	Very High Impact
5. Environmental Design as Crime Deterrent	3.5	High Impact
6. Impact of Police Presence on Crime Rates	4.45	Very High Impact
7. Rehabilitation vs. Punishment in Crime Deterrence	3.85	High Impact
8. Socioeconomic Targeting in Crime Deterrence	3.25	Slight Impact
9. Combining Technology and Community for Crime Reduction	3.9	High Impact
10. Cost-Effectiveness of Crime Deterrence Strategies	4.1	High Impact
Over-all Impact	3.94	High Impact

Table 3 presents the effectiveness ratings of various crime deterrence strategies, highlighting their impact on property crime reduction. The strategies were evaluated on a scale, with higher scores indicating a more substantial impact. The results show that community engagement in crime prevention had the highest effectiveness, receiving a score of 4.75, indicating a *very high impact* on reducing crime rates. Similarly, the effectiveness of crime deterrence strategies and the impact of police presence on crime rates both scored 4.45, also reflecting a *very high impact*.

Other strategies, including surveillance's role in crime reduction (3.7), smart home technology and crime prevention (3.55), environmental design as a crime deterrent (3.5), and rehabilitation vs. punishment in crime deterrence (3.85), were rated as having a *high impact*. Combining technology and community for crime reduction received a score of 3.9, also categorized as a *high impact*, indicating the effectiveness of an integrated approach.

In contrast, socioeconomic targeting in crime deterrence had a lower score of 3.25, categorized as having only a *slight impact*, suggesting that this strategy may be less effective than others. Lastly, the cost-effectiveness of crime deterrence strategies scored 4.1, reflecting a *high impact* and indicating the importance of sustainable, financially viable methods for long-term crime reduction.

Overall, the strategies evaluated in Table 3 resulted in an average score of 3.94, which falls within the *high-impact* category. This demonstrates that most of these deterrence methods are effective in addressing property crime.

Table 4. Correlation Between Perceived Effectiveness of Deterrence Strategies and Its Impact on Property Crime Rates

Correlation Coefficient (r)	t-statistic	Critical t-value (0.05 level)	Statistical Significance
0.858848	18.21	1.98	Significant

The computed t-statistic for the correlation coefficient $r=0.858848$ with 120 respondents is approximately 18.21. This value is significantly higher than the critical t-value of 1.98 at the 0.05 significance level. Since the computed t-statistic exceeds the critical value, the correlation between the variables is considered statistically significant. This suggests that a strong and meaningful relationship exists between the variables being studied, and the likelihood that this result occurred by chance is very low. Therefore, the correlation is not only strong but also reliable and significant at the given confidence level. This means that as one variable increases, the other variable also tends to increase. In the context of deterrence strategies and their impact on crime rates (if we assume these are the variables), a solid positive correlation suggests that the higher perceived effectiveness of deterrence strategies is associated with a more significant impact on reducing property crime rates.

The high correlation coefficient (close to 1) indicates a strong linear relationship between the variables, meaning changes in one variable are closely aligned with changes in the other. The statistical significance of this relationship, confirmed by the t-statistic (18.21), shows that the observed correlation is not due to random chance but reflects a proper relationship between the effectiveness of deterrence strategies and their impact on crime reduction. According to the data, effective deterrence strategies will likely significantly lower property crime rates.

Discussion

The analysis reveals that strategies such as increased police visibility, improved street lighting, and stricter law enforcement were perceived to have the most significant impact, with respondents rating both effectiveness and impact highly. Overall, the results suggest that implementing these strategies can significantly reduce property crime, demonstrating the critical role of both law enforcement and community-based efforts in crime prevention. The statistical analysis confirms that this relationship is reliable and not due to random chance, emphasizing the importance of these deterrence measures in enhancing public safety.

Findings

The study revealed significant findings regarding the perceptions of the respondents in Trinidad, Bohol, regarding the effectiveness of property crime deterrence strategies and the impact of these measures on property crime in their community:

1. Demographic Characteristics of Respondents

The demographic profile of the respondents showed that 54.17% were male, while 45.83% were female, reflecting a relatively balanced gender representation. The age group distribution revealed that most participants were between 31 and 45 (41.67%), followed by 33.33% in the 18-30 age group. The least represented group was those aged 61 and above, accounting for only 8.33%. This information is significant because different demographic groups might have varying perspectives on crime prevention, depending on factors like age and gender. For instance, younger or middle-aged respondents may be more active in community patrols, while older respondents may rely more on strategies like improved street lighting for safety.

2. Perceptions Regarding the Effectiveness of Deterrence Strategies

The respondents rated various crime deterrence strategies, and the overall mean score was 3.86, indicating that most strategies were perceived as *effective*. Stricter Law Enforcement (e.g., checkpoints) received the highest rating, with a mean score of 4.30, indicating that respondents view increased enforcement as a critical tool in crime prevention. Increased Police Visibility (4.20) and Improved Street

Lighting (4.10) were also rated highly, suggesting that visible, proactive policing and environmental measures such as better lighting significantly enhance public safety. On the other hand, Crime Prevention Education Programs were perceived as only *moderately effective*, with a score of 3.40, implying that while these programs are beneficial, they may not have an immediate or direct effect on reducing crime, especially when compared to more tangible or direct measures such as law enforcement or technology.

3. Impact of Deterrence Strategies on Property Crime Rates

The findings from the analysis of Table 3 reveal key insights into the effectiveness of various crime deterrence strategies in reducing property crime rates. Community engagement in crime prevention emerged as the most impactful strategy, with a *high impact* score of 4.75. This underscores the importance of community involvement in reducing property crime, as it likely fosters stronger neighborhood vigilance, cooperation with law enforcement, and enhanced social cohesion. Similarly, the effectiveness of crime deterrence strategies and the impact of police presence on crime rates received scores of 4.45, also categorized as *very high impact*. These findings highlight the significant role of structured deterrence plans and a visible police presence in deterring property crime.

Other strategies, such as surveillance's role in crime reduction (3.7), smart home technology and crime prevention (3.55), environmental design as a crime deterrent (3.5), rehabilitation vs. punishment in crime deterrence (3.85), and combining technology and community for crime reduction (3.9), were all rated as having a *high impact*. This suggests that technological, environmental, and rehabilitative approaches contribute meaningfully to crime reduction, though their impact is less substantial than community engagement or police presence.

The cost-effectiveness of crime deterrence strategies, with a score of 4.1, further emphasizes the importance of balancing effectiveness with financial sustainability in long-term crime prevention efforts. In contrast, socioeconomic targeting in crime deterrence, with a score of 3.25, was the least effective strategy, reflecting only a *slight impact*. This indicates that focusing solely on socioeconomic factors in crime deterrence may not lead to significant reductions in property crime, pointing to the need for more comprehensive, multifaceted approaches.

Overall, the average score of 3.94 suggests that most of the assessed strategies have a *high impact* on reducing property crime rates, with community-based initiatives, strategic law enforcement, and integrated technological solutions being the most effective approaches.

4. Relationship Between Perceived Effectiveness and the Impact of Deterrence Strategies on Property Crime Rates

A statistical analysis examined the relationship between the perceived effectiveness of deterrence strategies and their impact on property crime rates. The Pearson correlation coefficient was 0.8588, indicating a strong positive relationship between the two variables. This means that as the perceived effectiveness of deterrence strategies increases, so does their perceived impact on reducing property crime rates. The t-statistic of 18.21, much higher than the critical value of 1.98 at the 0.05 significance level, confirms that this correlation is statistically significant. This result implies that when residents believe a deterrence strategy is effective, it is more likely to have a noticeable and meaningful impact on property crime reduction. Such a finding reinforces the importance of implementing strategies the community views as effective, as these are more likely to lead to tangible crime reduction outcomes. Strategies that combine law enforcement, community engagement, and technology, such as surveillance cameras and checkpoints, offer the most significant potential for reducing property crime.

Conclusion

The study revealed several key insights into the perceptions and effectiveness of property crime deterrence strategies in Trinidad and Bohol. First, the demographic profile of respondents, which was pretty balanced in gender and predominantly composed of working-age individuals, suggests that crime prevention strategies must cater to a diverse population with varying safety concerns. Regarding deterrence strategies, stricter law enforcement, increased police visibility, and improved street lighting were perceived as the most effective measures, underscoring the importance of visible, proactive

policing and environmental modifications in enhancing public safety. While community engagement emerged as the most impactful strategy in reducing property crime, technological solutions such as surveillance cameras and smart home technologies were also considered beneficial, though slightly less impactful. A significant positive relationship was found between the perceived effectiveness of deterrence strategies and their actual impact on crime reduction, as evidenced by a strong correlation. This reinforces the importance of implementing strategies the community views as effective, as they are more likely to lead to tangible reductions in property crime rates. The findings suggest that law enforcement presence, community involvement, and technological interventions offer the most comprehensive and practical approach to reducing property crime in Trinidad and Bohol.

Recommendations

Based on the findings and conclusions of this study, the following recommendations are proposed:

1. Increase Police Presence and Visibility. Expand the coverage and frequency of police patrols, particularly in crime hotspots. Utilize data-driven strategies to deploy law enforcement in areas with high rates of theft or vandalism. A visible police presence can effectively deter criminal activity and enhance the community's sense of safety.

2. Strengthen and Expand Neighborhood Watch Programs. Encourage broader participation in neighborhood watch initiatives by providing regular training and organizing meetings for residents. Equip community members with skills for identifying and reporting suspicious activities and coordinate with local authorities for scheduled community patrols to increase vigilance and deter crime.

3. Upgrade Surveillance and Environmental Infrastructure. Increase the installation of CCTV cameras in strategic locations such as commercial areas and known crime hotspots. Regularly maintain the equipment for optimal functioning. Additionally, improving street lighting in poorly lit areas and well-lit environments has been proven to deter crime, prioritizing energy-efficient lighting that remains operational during outages.

4. Enhance Crime Prevention Education Programs. Redesign educational initiatives to make them more interactive and relevant to community concerns. Implement workshops and awareness campaigns focusing on practical safety tips and the role of citizens in crime prevention. Collaborate with schools and local organizations to deliver targeted programs for different demographic groups, including youth and seniors.

5. Implement Targeted Interventions for High-Risk Areas. Focus on area-specific strategies such as installing barriers or gates in high-risk residential zones. Incentivize businesses to invest in security measures and establish rapid-response crime prevention teams to address emerging crime trends or spikes in particular areas.

These recommendations aim to address the ongoing property crime challenges in Trinidad and Bohol by strengthening existing strategies and incorporating new approaches that foster a proactive and community-oriented crime prevention culture. Implementing these measures can contribute to a safer environment, enhance the quality of life for residents, and build stronger community resilience against crime.

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